

Integrating GIS, Remote Sensing, and Hydrological Models for Effective Flood Risk Mitigation and Water Resource Management

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Abstract: This review delivers various hydrological modelling approaches in different atmospheres, with a focus on watershed modelling systems (WMS), highlighting important hydrological and hydraulic modelling techniques for investigating watershed water dynamics. Hydrological models are essential for assessing how water moves and is distributed at both local and catchment levels. These models are designed to mimic the interaction between rainfall and runoff, providing valuable insights for city planners and hydrologists into the complex processes occurring in urban and catchment environments. It provides a basic knowledge of empirical equations for runoff calculations and discusses two-dimensional (2D) modelling. This review identifies the main components of hydrological modelling, including loss methods, direct runoff, and 2D analysis. It has been determined that the Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) and the Hydrologic Engineering Center-Hydrologic Modelling System (HEC-HMS) are the models most frequently employed. Additionally, the Hydrologic Engineering Center-River Analysis System (HEC-RAS) is recognized for its proficiency in performing both 1D and 2D hydraulic modeling, particularly for evaluating floodplains. Hydrological models are vital tools for evaluating flood risks in both observed and unobserved catchment areas.

Keywords: Hydrological Modelling, Hydraulic Modelling, Watershed Modelling Systems, HEC-HMS, SWAT, HEC-RAS

1 Introduction

Lately, there has been an enhanced significance among researchers on the study of hydrology due to its importance to both social and physical surroundings [1]. Hydrological models, a subset of geoscience, play a pivotal role in guiding the water resources planning and development [2] and contribute to discussions on water control [3], [4]. These models are crucial for forecasting and flood prediction [5] and for managing, predicting, and understanding catchment water resources [6]. They are necessary for water resource assessment, including environmental protection [7], by analyzing nonlinear and complex relationships between empirical runoff estimation models and various variables [8]. There has been an widening use of hydrological modeling frameworks in both humid and arid regions to analyze how various factors influence runoff and the distribution of water [9]. They play an essential role in analyzing the effects of modern anthropogenic factors on hydrologic regimes [10], investigating the effects of land use and land cover on runoff and flood inundation [11], and examining the effects of human activities on runoff [12]. With the advent of remote sensing (RS) data, the application of hydrological models has improved, allowing for better prediction of stream features and peak discharge [13]. Hydrological models are valuable for urban catchment management and flood risk reduction, particularly in developed nations with accessible data [14]. In developing

countries, remote sensing data can enhance flood simulations and integrate them into hydrological models (HMs) [15]. The combination of the Watershed Modelling System (WMS) with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) has enhanced the accuracy of water management predictions across different scales [16]. This review offers a basic introduction to theoretical hydrology modeling from a geographical perspective and is organized into four parts: a general classification of hydrology, an overview of key models, the use of hydrology and hydraulic models, and the consequences for catchments without gauges.

2. Methodology

Models for hydrology and hydraulics have been created to evaluate and simulate the movement of water, focusing on how rainfall is distributed across surface, subsurface, and underground areas. The purpose of this study was to investigate the use of these models by examining a variety of articles available on Google Scholar and SCOPUS. The study concentrated on the phrases “hydrology modelling,” “runoff models,” “hydrodynamic model,” “ungauged-catchment,” and “ungauged-basin.” This research also reviewed a substantial collection of articles on hydrology and hydraulic models to explore their use in different environmental settings. The snowball technique was also utilized to track down articles referenced in the chosen papers.

2.1 Evolution and Classification of Hydrological Models

In the mid-19th century, the development of hydrological models for managing water resources commenced with rational methods designed to estimate the connection between rainfall and runoff. [17]. With the surge in urban populations, there has been a marked rise in the demand for water resources and urban land, highlighting the need for environmental modeling to grasp these evolving dynamics. Hydrological models provide a simplified numerical representation of the hydrological system [18], are designed to illustrate surface streamflow and subsurface processes, and are key tools in water resource management. These models are crucial because of the limitations of direct hydrological measurement methods, which enhance our understanding of the streamflow frequency and water movement. They are extensively used to estimate runoff volume and peak discharge under various environmental conditions, such as in humid and arid regions [19]. For over 165 years, hydrological modelling has been applied to study land changes from rural to urban areas, which typically result in increased erosion, storm runoff, and changes in discharge and travel time owing to surface soil changes [20].

Hydrological modelling is generally developed for damp regions [21] and covers a wide range of applications, including flood studies (planning and designing hydraulic structures, evaluating existing structures, preparing for flood damage reduction, and controlling floodplain activities) and storage studies (analyzing catchment and reservoir yields and water resource potential) [22]. These models are divided into three primary categories according to spatial resolution: Distributed, Semi-Distributed, and Lumped. They are competent of simulating runoff within the boundaries of a catchment area [23]. They are also categorized by model structure (empirical, conceptual, and physical models) and spatial resolution processing (Lumped, Semi-Distributed, and Distributed models) [24].

The application of hydrological models spans surface water, urban hydrology, and groundwater, and the choice of model depends on the data availability and accuracy [25]. Fig. 1

illustrates the classification of hydrological models based on both methods and resolutions, highlighting the importance of selecting an appropriate model based on the study objectives [93].

Fig. 1 Classification of hydrological models [93]

2.2 Comparative Analysis of Hydrological Models for Runoff Prediction and Flood Risk Assessment in Changing Environments

In recent times, there has been a significant rise in urbanization worldwide, affecting both developing and developed nations. Although this growth brings advantages to human life, such as contemporary housing, it also presents considerable environmental and ecological challenges, including air pollution, the loss of natural ground cover, and the disruption of hydrological systems. This review explores the use of hydrological models categorized by spatial resolution, concentrating on distributed, semi-distributed, and lumped models.

2.2.1 Evaluating the Effectiveness of HEC-HMS for Hydrological Simulations and Flood Risk Assessment

The HEC-HMS model, created by the US Army Corps of Engineers Hydrology, is intended to replicate how precipitation runoff occurs within watershed systems. This model can represent a range of geographical regions, from extensive river basins to smaller urban or natural watersheds [26]. It has been widely applied to model and predict stream flows in watersheds that are humid, have varied topography, or are arid [27]. Cheng et al. [28] explored the use of the HEC-HMS model and its parameter regionalization for small, ungauged watersheds in the hilly areas of Henan Province, China. The analysis reveals that the HEC-HMS model effectively simulates the rainfall-runoff process in small watersheds. Moreover, the regionalization approach is advantageous for inferring model parameters for small, ungauged watersheds in these hilly terrains. In a related investigation, Hamdan et al. [26] utilized the HEC-HMS hydrological model, integrating GIS and a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), to replicate the rainfall-runoff dynamics and evaluate the discharge in the Al-Adhaim River basin in Iraq. The model exhibited a strong alignment between the observed and simulated hydrographs, achieving a 90% coefficient of determination during both the calibration and verification phases, highlighting its suitability for hydrological simulations in the area.

The system data describes the watershed region inside the basin model. The meteorological model employed in this research incorporated the data necessary for precipitation and evapotranspiration, which are vital for modeling watershed processes. While HEC-HMS can simulate infiltration from the land surface, it does not have the ability to model storage and vertical water movement within the soil layer. Rather, it integrates near-surface and overland flows, considering them as direct runoff [29]. As land use (LU) underwent changes, Szwagrzyk et al. [30] investigated how these LU alterations impacted flood risk in the Ropa River Basin, a 1000 km² area in Poland. Utilizing the Soil Conservation Services – Curve Number (SCS-CN) and HEC-HMS models, they created a range of scenarios to evaluate the future impacts of land use on flood risk, ultimately determining that flood risk is likely to increase. The HEC-HMS model has been applied in diverse environmental contexts to examine the effects of climate change, land use (LU), and land cover (LC) on runoff and peak discharge (PD). Therefore, the HEC-HMS model is regarded as a crucial hydrological tool for calculating unit hydrographs (UH) in watersheds. Cheah et al. [31] devised a geospatial modelling methodology employing GIS, SCS-CN, and HEC-HMS to estimate the peak flood discharge in Selangor, Malaysia. This method showed a strong alignment with the Clark unit hydrograph simulation and provided an effective way to estimate the peak flood discharge without relying on a hydrodynamic model. Both automatic and manual calibration methods have been demonstrated to be effective for HEC-HMSs [32].

2.2.2 SWAT Model Applications in Evaluating Hydrological Responses to Environmental Changes

The SWAT model has been extensively utilized in a range of environmental settings. Originally developed to support the research initiatives of the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) and the Agricultural Research Service (ARS) [33], the SWAT model aids in estimating and calculating runoff through two main approaches: the Soil Conservation Service-Curve Number (SCS-CN) and Green-Ampt (GA) methods [34]. According to Haleem et al. [35], in the Upper Indus Basin of Pakistan, the influence of climate change on river runoff is more pronounced (61.61%) compared to the effect of land-use change (38.39%). Forecasts suggest that future runoff depth will rise due to both climate and land use changes, with climate change exerting a more significant influence (12.76–25.92%) compared to land use change (0.37–1.1%). This study underscores the necessity of incorporating both climate and land-use changes into water resource management strategies to ensure sustainability. A study employing the SWAT model in a watershed in a Brazilian tropical forest demonstrated that transforming forests into croplands or pastures had a negligible effect on runoff, whereas deforestation led to a modest increase in runoff. Future climate projections suggest a general decline in runoff, with only slight differences across various emission scenarios [36]. The analysis conducted using the SWAT model on the watershed of the Feiling Hydrological Station indicated that variations in precipitation exerted a more substantial influence on runoff than changes in temperature. Scenarios involving extreme land use changes, such as cropland expansion, resulted in increased runoff, whereas scenarios involving increased woodland led to a reduction in runoff. These findings underscore the necessity for enhanced management of soil and water resources [37].

The model was utilized to investigate how human activities, including land use (LU), impact runoff. Tan et al. [38] explored the impact of land use and climate change on the hydrological patterns of the Johor River Basin (JRB) in Malaysia by employing the SWAT

model. In a similar study, Bekele et al. [39] investigated how changes in land use and land cover (LULC) affect hydrological processes within the Keleta watershed, which is part of Ethiopia's Awash River Basin, by employing the SWAT model. From 1985 to 2010, there was a 10.4% rise in surface runoff, a 0.6% increase in base flow, and a 3.5% decline in groundwater flow. These alterations, caused by inappropriate land use practices, present considerable threats to water resources, ecosystems, and infrastructure, highlighting the critical need for thorough land management strategies. Lucas-Borja et al. [36] utilized the SWAT model to assess how changes in land use and climate scenarios impact runoff generation in a tropical forest watershed located in Brazil. After calibrating the model with 20 years of data, the simulations indicated that converting forests to crops or pastures had a minimal impact on runoff, whereas complete deforestation led to a slight increase. Under projected climate scenarios, runoff is anticipated to decrease with minimal variation across different emission pathways. Among the land uses, bare soil generated the highest runoff, whereas pasture generated the lowest runoff.

The SWAT is an essential instrument for modeling the impacts of land use (LU) alterations, especially concerning runoff and underground water behavior. Iqbal et al. [40] investigated how changes in climate and land use affect hydrological processes in the Yellow River's Source Region. The results indicated that climate change has a more pronounced impact than changes in land use, resulting in significant decreases in runoff and increases in evapotranspiration. This effect was particularly pronounced in the Maqu sub-basin, where runoff decreased by 18% and ET increased by 10.4%. In a similar study, Paive et al. [41] employed the SWAT model to assess the impact of deforestation in Peru's Madre de Dios Basin. Transforming 12% of the forested region into barren land led to a 38% rise in monthly surface runoff, a 1% reduction in yearly evapotranspiration, and a 12% increase in streamflow. The Inambari sub-basin experienced the most significant changes, highlighting the increased flood risks and potential ecosystem disruption. Briones et al. [42] carried out research to assess how changes in land use and land cover (LULC) affect the hydrology of the Palico watershed in the Philippines, utilizing the SWAT model for their analysis. The study showed that deforestation and the loss of rangelands resulted in an increase in surface runoff while reducing base flow and groundwater replenishment. In contrast, the restoration of forests had a reverse impact, highlighting the essential importance of balanced land use planning for maintaining water sustainability. Haleem et al. [35] utilized the SWAT model to assess the separate and combined impacts of anticipated climate and land use changes on surface runoff in the Upper Indus Basin of Pakistan. The findings indicated that climate change exerted a more significant impact (up to 25.92%) on future runoff than land use change (up to 1.1%). The combination of these elements leads to heightened runoff, highlighting the importance of adopting comprehensive water resource management plans.

2.2.3 Comparative Analysis of 1D and 2D Hydrodynamic Models in Flood Zone Mapping and Urban Flood Risk Management

Hydrodynamic models in one dimension are widely employed to evaluate flood levels and flow rates in stream networks. HEC-RAS is an essential hydraulic model used to understand water depth and distribution across a terrain. Both 1D and 2D hydrodynamic models serve as efficient hydrological routing techniques, enabling the swift evaluation of distributed water levels and flows in branched and structured stream networks. They achieve this by taking into account elements like backwater effects, weather variations, and dispersion [43].

In hydrodynamic models that describe water distributions in one or two dimensions, parameters are usually set using a sequence of channel cross-sections that are perpendicular to the flow and the floodplain's topography. These can be acquired through a ground survey at a reasonable expense. Two-dimensional models consider the flow directions in both horizontal planes, enabling more precise estimations of water levels along the watercourse [44]. This resulted in improved predictions of potential flooding and the volume of water existing in the virtual channel. Additionally, water departing from the main channel can be directed through levees or overbanks depending on the flow direction and modifications to the flow path.

Utilizing improved remote sensing data, the HEC-RAS 2D model was applied to predict flood zones. This model primarily relies on a digital elevation model (DEM), rainfall information, and boundary conditions as its main input data [45]. The use of these models for standard waterway floodplains has expanded in scope, encompassing both the stream's length and the model's spatial resolution or the DEM employed to depict the channel and floodplain's topography. As a result, this method has become increasingly popular in flood modeling, especially in areas with intricate floodplain landscapes. To estimate the water depth in urban areas accurately, a 1D/2D model should be used to determine the water depth and establish a flood risk map [46].

Waseem et al. [47] demonstrated that combining hydrological models with advanced remote sensing (RS) data and geographic information systems (GIS) significantly improves the accuracy of flood risk assessments. Huțanu et al. [48] conducted a comprehensive flood vulnerability assessment for the Jijia floodplain in Romania, utilizing 1D HEC-RAS hydraulic modelling alongside high-resolution LiDAR-derived DEMs. The results indicated that, in contrast to official maps that utilized less detailed data and MIKE SHE modeling, the HEC-RAS model offered a more accurate and realistic representation of flood risks for 100- and 1000-year flood scenarios, thereby enhancing local flood mitigation strategies. Iroume et al. [49] conducted a study using a 2D HEC-RAS model to simulate a severe flood event that occurred on August 21, 2020, in Makèpè Missokè, Douala, Cameroon. The model accurately reproduced the flood's characteristics, including its reach, depth of up to 4.48 meters, and velocity under 1 meter per second, closely aligning with the observed data. This highlights the model's dependability for assessing future flood risks and guiding urban development in the area. Chen et al. [50] conducted a study utilizing the SIPSON/UIM integrated 1D-2D model to evaluate the impacts of pluvial and fluvial flooding in Stockbridge, Keighley, UK. The findings indicate that combined flooding scenarios, including sewer overflow and river overtopping or breaching, result in the most severe surface flooding, with different flood drivers affecting various areas.

3.1 Applications of Watershed Modeling System (WMS) in Hydrological Analysis and Water Resource Management

Hydrological models provide an advanced scientific representation of the hydrological system, designed to replicate the behavior of surface water and groundwater, serving as essential tools for the regulation and administration of water resources [51]. The Watershed Modelling System (WMS) is built on two core disciplines, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and hydrology, which aid in the identification of watershed data and support hydrological analyses [52]. As computer technology advances, the precision and relevance of hydrological models continue to improve [53].

Hydrological models play a crucial role in improving our comprehension of streamflow patterns. Most of the hydrological data were analyzed using the Watershed Modelling System (WMS), which involves a) identifying catchment parameters and boundaries, and b) processing the data through the software's interface. The WMS was created to aid in watershed analysis and acts as an essential instrument for handling hydrological data and converting large volumes of information into a Geographic Information System (GIS) format [54]. Consequently, several factors must be considered when selecting the hydrological models. The implementation of WMS in hydrological studies offers numerous advantages. Rai et al. [55] performed a study on the Varuna River Basin in India, utilizing a GIS-based morphometric evaluation to assess its drainage features. The basin was segmented into three distinct sub-watersheds, and 41 parameters concerning drainage, geometry, texture, and relief were assessed. This research highlights the influence of morphometry on soil and topography, offering valuable insights for watershed planning, natural resource management, and drainage development.

After defining the boundaries of the catchment, calculating the morphological and morphometric areas of the catchment yields crucial information for analyzing and assessing the study region. This process has been facilitated by the watershed modeling system (WMS) model. In hydrological research, the characteristics of a catchment are crucial for simulating runoff and flood-prone areas. Hydrological and catchment management are fundamentally based on these traits, which encompass geomorphological and morphometric characteristics. The WMS is particularly advantageous for analyzing catchment features. Once the basin boundary is extracted, this software offers various functionalities such as preparing data for numerous hydrological applications. Fig. 2 shows the application of the WMS across various hydrological domains. The WMS is an indispensable model for watershed analysis and data preparation in GIS programs [94].

Fig. 2 Application of WMS across various hydrological domains [94]

Hydrological and hydraulic models have been developed to analyze water movement, runoff, and inundation patterns [56]. These models require various input data including soil hydrology, land use (LU), land cover (LC), elevation, geomorphology, and rainfall. Hydrological

parameters and catchment boundaries, along with their morphometric and geometric dimensions, can be determined using WMS. Elewa et al. [57] have shown that this model has been utilized in various catchment areas. In their research, they pinpointed appropriate sites for runoff water harvesting (RWH) within the Wadi Watir watershed located in the Sinai Peninsula. This was achieved through an integrated method that incorporated AHP, GIS, WMS, and remote sensing. Eight hydrological parameters were employed to develop a multiparametric spatial model that was validated using the consistency ratio and topographic wetness index. The model classified RWH potential into five categories, with 33.24% of the area deemed highly suitable, leading to the proposal of four retention dams and seven cisterns for sustainable water management in arid regions. Similarly, Fathy et al. [51] developed an integrated model utilizing GIS, WMS, and GMS to manage surface and groundwater resources in the arid Wadi Watier region of southern Sinai, Egypt. This study proposed the construction of 14 dams—five designated for storage and nine for groundwater recharge—capable of collecting up to 160.72 million meters of rainwater. This initiative aimed to enhance flood protection and alleviate water scarcity in the study area.

3.2 Comparative Analysis of Hydrological Models

Hydrological and hydraulic models are integral to environmental research, particularly for examining the dynamics of the water cycle and its interactions with terrestrial and subterranean environments. These models are essential for comprehending water-related issues in both surface and subsurface domains [51]. They play a crucial role in assessing how basins respond to rainfall and the impact of land use on hydrological systems [58]. In addition, hydrological models have been utilized to explore how climate change affects runoff and peak discharge, as illustrated by Bronstert et al. [59]. These models excel in predicting different runoff components, such as a) Runoff Volume, b) Direct Runoff, c) Base Flow, and d) Channel Flow [60]. Hydrological models employ various techniques to simulate and generate unit hydrographs. The estimation of runoff and flooding at any catchment level and under varying conditions can be accomplished using different models, contingent upon the study objectives and the quality of the data available.

The hydrological model is applicable across various environmental contexts, including arid, semi-arid, and humid zones [61]. Hydraulic models that utilize one-dimensional water depth and two-dimensional water distribution can simulate flooding and inundation events [96]. Flooding after runoff can result from severe weather, climate change, and alterations in land use and land cover (LULC) [62]. These models improve the comprehension of hydrology and catchment planning, thus aiding in better water management [63]. The primary focus of the hydrological model is to comprehend and predict water movement at the catchment level [64]. Fig. 3 demonstrates these applications for hydrology and hydraulic models, encompassing the peak discharge and flow direction [96].

Fig. 3 Hydrology/Hydraulic Models [96]

Following precipitation, surface water movement is influenced by factors such as the degree of slope in each land area, gravitational forces, water retention capacity, and land morphology. Typically, the primary inquiry pertains to the water flow direction. Hydraulic modelling is frequently employed in the study of hydrodynamics and environmental engineering. A wide range of hydrodynamic modelling types are currently available, spanning from relatively simple hydraulic models (Water DI-D models) to complex two-dimensional models that consider flow directions. Simulations of water depth and velocity have become essential components of two-dimensional modelling [65] and inundation mapping [66]. Most hydrodynamic flood models can simulate flood flows in both one-dimensional and two-dimensional formats.

The one-dimensional (1D) model assumes that floodwaters move along the channel's length, with the channel's shape depicted by cross-sectional lines that can be automatically derived from a Digital Terrain Model (DTM). Each type of model possessed unique features, such as assumptions, input parameters, and outputs. The characteristics of the route's roughness are represented as points along the cross-sectional lines, with each cross section receiving a single value. The computational method calculated the mean speed and the depth of floodwater at each cross-section. Following this, the surface water profile was assessed in relation to the height of the channel banks on both the left and right sides. While the 1D model is recognized for its numerical stability and computational efficiency, it falls short in accurately representing complex topographies. Regardless of the source of flooding, the extent and depth of flooding were predominantly predicted using numerical modelling [67].

Hydrological models are essential tools for examining complex interactions between water, soil, climate, and land use (LU). These models are instrumental in studying water movement within catchment areas by considering their geomorphological and morphometric characteristics. The rational method is widely recognized in hydrology because of its simplified approach to runoff analysis, particularly in small catchments [68]. Utilizing these models allows researchers to effectively tackle important hydrological issues, such as calculating runoff discharge in cubic meters per second (m^3/s) and determining the direction of water flow.

In hydrology modeling, the initial question involves identifying which strategies are beneficial to implement from the four primary categories of computational processes. These categories include: a) calculating excess rainfall or runoff volume, b) computing direct runoff, c) determining baseflow, and e) the final one, which is channel flow routing computation.

Nevertheless, each computational procedure encompasses multiple calculation techniques. The second inquiry pertains to employing 1D/2D models to examine water depth and distribution [46].

Hydrological models play a pivotal role in estimating runoff from precipitation, which involves the movement of water through channels. These models are crucial for replicating the impacts of different elements, such as land use and land cover, on runoff and peak discharge. However, there is a need to improve the use of hydrological models, especially in dry areas, due to limitations in data availability [69]. As shown in Fig. 4, the Unit Hydrograph (UH) is an essential factor in a catchment area that represents peak discharge through hydrological models [98]. Grasping the concept of peak discharge is crucial in hydrology for assessing and forecasting flood levels [31]. The UH illustrates the impact of soil type, land use, land cover, precipitation, and geological features on peak discharge [70]. Additionally, the UH exhibits a range of forms and contours that differ between the dry and wet regions. Hydrological models are useful for simulating runoff, forecasting flood characteristics using the UH, and assessing how land use and human activities affect the quality of catchment areas [71]. These models can be utilized in a variety of environmental conditions, such as dry, semi-dry, and wet regions. UH plays a crucial role in numerous hydrological studies, including flood estimation and assessing flood risk [72]. For instance, Loaiciga noted that in arid regions, the UH's peak curve appeared sooner, while it occurred in the middle of the curve [73].

Fig. 4 Unit Hydrograph in different environmental conditions [98]

The charts presented above were derived from extensive review papers. During brief rainfall events, the peak discharge occurred rapidly, akin to flash flooding. Conversely, in humid regions, the peak discharge follows a more typical curve. This variation may be attributed to differences in soil conditions and physical properties. Paula Netto et al. [74] conducted a comparative analysis of SWAT and HEC-HMS hydrological models to assess their efficacy under varying watershed conditions. This study revealed that SWAT demonstrated superior

performance in regions characterized by high flow, abundant data, and hydrological variability, whereas HEC-HMS was more effective in low-flow and data-scarce environments. This study underscores the critical role of model selection in optimizing watershed management and disaster-mitigation strategies.

Fig.5 Hydrological Model-based Resolution Wadi Sudr is a wadi located in the southwest of Sinai, depicted as (a) Lumped, (b) Semi Distributed, and (c) Distributed model [99]

Figure 5 depicts the main hydrological model, which relies on data inputs like land use (LU), rainfall data, topographical features, and soil classifications. This model can be divided into three categories: A) lumped, B) semi-distributed, and C) distributed models. Additionally, these models can be utilized at three distinct resolutions: a) lumped, b) semi-distributed, and c) distributed [99].

Furthermore, hydrological models enhance the understanding of runoff, peak discharge, and flooding across various catchment characteristics. Utilizing a variety of hydrological models can improve the evaluations made by hydrologists when they use two or more models. For example, Aliye et al. [75] evaluated the performance of two hydrological models, SWAT and HEC-HMS, in replicating runoff in Ethiopia's Katar Basin. They determined that HEC-HMS exhibited excellent predictive capabilities in this region. In a study by Sith and Nadaoka [76], the effectiveness of GSSHA and SWAT was assessed in forecasting streamflow and suspended sediment levels within a small agricultural watershed in Japan. Their research indicated that although both models have advantages in simulating floods, SWAT typically performed better than GSSHA over longer durations.

On a macro scale, such as catchment areas, lumped models serve as practical tools for analyzing runoff. Conversely, on a microscale, such as in an urban area, the distributed model yields more precise results. Utilizing a hydrological model grounded in specific techniques is the most efficient method for evaluating the effects of land use (LU) and land cover (LC) on runoff and peak discharge [77]. These models are instrumental in examining changes in LU and LC and their effects on runoff in the watershed.

With the integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and hydrological models like HEC-HMS and HEC-RAS, conducting extensive hydrological research at the catchment scale has become increasingly achievable. These models are especially useful for predicting runoff and flooding, as illustrated in the San Antonio River Basin, which covers roughly 4,000 square miles (10,000 km²) in Central Texas, USA [78]. As a result, hydrological models can be utilized in both measured and unmeasured catchments to predict runoff and guide flood management plans [79]. Various methods and models are available for studying water movement

across catchments of different sizes, which are influenced by factors such as topography, geology, and vegetation cover [80].

3.3 Remote Sensing and GIS Applications in Runoff Simulation for Data-Scarce Watersheds

Predicting runoff is an essential but challenging task in the field of surface hydrology. This is especially important in headwater basins, as these areas frequently act as the main sources of water for their surrounding regions. Predicting runoff with precision is crucial for managing water resources, safeguarding human lives, supporting agriculture, industry, and environmental sustainability, as well as for the development of infrastructure [81]. Consequently, there has been a marked increase in the study of runoff in ungauged catchments, as evidenced by recent publications in various journals [82]. Globally, there are numerous ungauged catchments where direct streamflow data monitoring is unavailable.

Globally, most catchments remain ungauged, resulting in a lack of hydrological observational data [83]. Moreover, the estimation of catchment parameters and evaluation processes enhances our understanding of the flow characteristics in ungauged basins [84]. Gaining a thorough understanding of the characteristics of catchment systems, including their hydrological processes, is essential for enhancing water resource management (WRM). These encompass elements such as (a) the topography of catchment areas, (b) the level of urban development, (c) the size or configuration of basins, (d) the total volume and duration of precipitation in upstream and mountainous regions, (e) the variability of soil permeability within river channels, (f) differences in runoff characteristics in wadi basins, and (g) the lack of data and constraints in methods for predicting flash floods [85]. In gauged basins, the typical calibration approach, referred to as classical calibration, frequently depends on hydrological and precipitation data that are either outdated or unreliable, and are geographically or temporally distant from the area under study. Hydrological model calibration in ungauged watersheds can be achieved using various data sources and methods [86]. Ungauged catchments are found in arid and humid environments worldwide [87]. For instance, the Imjin catchment, which spans North and South Korea, is considered to be one of the most critical basins in the country. Management of flood in this area is challenging because of the constraints and sharing of hydrological data between the two countries [88]. In the expansive Asian country of Russia, around 2.6 million streams are either not monitored or have insufficient observation [89]. The Russian State Hydrometeorological University has created a third-generation multilayer conceptual model, known as MLCM3, designed specifically for Russian catchments that lack gauging. Zhang et al. [83] conducted two lumped models for simulations of runoff in 222 ungauged basins located in different zones of Australia. A global optimization of nine parameters in the SIMHYD model and fourteen parameters in the Xinjiang model was carried out using a genetic algorithm [83].

Even with a shortage of observational data, a range of techniques, such as physical models and cost-effective methods, have been used to simulate hydrological processes. The former simulates the transformation of rainfall into runoff, whereas the latter establishes statistical relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Flood frequency analysis is particularly useful for flood modelling in the absence of rainfall observations and water discharge data in ungauged catchments [90]. In ungauged catchments, multiple methods should be employed to evaluate and calibrate hydrological models, such as using remote sensing

(RS) data to map floods, which aids model calibration and validation and enhances management understanding, particularly in ungauged catchments [13]. Additionally, RS imagery can carry model evaluation in ungauged basins by delineating the watershed. To advance hydrological model calibration, Landsat imagery has been proposed as an alternative data source for observing floods from space, thereby benefiting the hydrological community in model calibration. The most prevalent factors influencing runoff modelling in ungauged basins are the land management and soil type practices [91].

To enhance hydrological models, it is essential to modify and adjust observational data. Huang et al. [13] demonstrated that bias-corrected remotely sensed AET data considerably enhanced the evaluation of water balance model for runoff prediction for ungauged basins. This study underscores the superiority of gridded RS-AET data over traditional methods, particularly for headwaters and large basins. In their study, Ibrahim-Bathis et al. [92] applied HEC-HMS alongside remote sensing and GIS technologies to replicate the stormwater runoff in Doddahalla watershed, an area without gauging stations. The validated model enabled dependable estimation of streamflow, which is necessary for water resource management in regions with scarce data. The HEC-HMS model can forecast runoff in catchments that lack gauging stations [93].

Conversely, ungauged catchments are characterized by a lack of observational hydrological data, that is a objection prevalent in both developing and developed nations. Such observational data are crucial for accurate hydrological modelling. In ungauged basins where hydrological data are scarce, the optimal approach for simulating runoff involves employing more than or equal to two hydrological models, particularly in state situated in semiarid and arid regions [81]. Two approaches were employed to model runoff: transferring data from the closest gauged catchment and using regional information. As a result, hydrological models have become crucial instruments for assessing and examining water resources and their cycles under a range of environmental conditions, both at catchment and local levels.

Zhang et al. [83] contended without empiric evidence in ungauged basins presents a significant challenge in hydrological studies, which complicates the prediction of runoff models. As a result, data-driven techniques have recently become a viable option for improving the generation and verification of hydrological models. These techniques strengthen the forecasting as well as verification about hydrological models. The combination of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has enhanced the ability to simulate and extract hydrological parameters, providing an alternative approach and tool for hydrological research, especially when observational data is lacking. This is due to crucial elements, namely the optimization of pretended water balance model outputs with essential reference data, which has led to extensive hydrological studies being conducted under diverse environmental conditions worldwide. This review presents several studies listed in Table 1. Moreover, the combination of Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) has enhanced the comprehension of simulating and extracting hydrological parameters. This integration provides an alternative approach and tool for hydrological research, especially when observational data is lacking. This is due to critical components, namely the optimization of modeled water balance model outputs using essential reference data, which has led to extensive hydrological studies being conducted under diverse environmental conditions worldwide.

Table 1: Provide an overview of various hydrology research conducted in both gauged and ungauged catchments across diverse environmental settings.

Author	Modelling Aims	Software	Environmental Condition	Basin Type	Catchment Location Country
Cheng et al. (2021)	Simulate runoff process	HEC-HMS	Hilly, semi-arid	Ungauged	Henan Province, China
Hamdan et al. (2021)	Model the rainfall-runoff process and evaluate the discharge	HEC-HMS	Arid	Gauged	Al-Adhaim, Iraq
Szwagrzyk et al. (2018)	Evaluate how changes in land use affect flood risk	HEC-HMS, SCS-CN	Humid	Gauged	Ropa River Basin, Poland
Cheah et al. (2019)	Estimate peak flood discharge	HEC-HMS, GIS, SCS-CN	Humid	Gauged	Selangor, Malaysia
Haleem et al. (2021)	Examine how changes in land use and climate affect runoff	SWAT	Arid	Gauged	Upper Indus Basin, Pakistan
Lucas-Borja et al. (2020)	Examine the effects of land use and climate changes on runoff	SWAT	Humid	Gauged	Tropical forest, Brazil
Bekele et al. (2021)	Examine how changes in land use and cover affect hydrology	SWAT	Humid	Gauged	Keleta watershed, Ethiopia
Iqbal et al. (2022)	Examine how hydrology is impacted by changes in climate and land use	SWAT	Arid	Gauged	Yellow River source region, China
Paiva et al. (2023)	Evaluate effects of deforestation on hydrology	SWAT	Humid	Gauged	Madre de Dios Basin, Peru
Briones et al. (2016)	Analyze how hydrology is affected by changes in land use and cover	SWAT	Humid	Gauged	Palico watershed, Philippines
Ibrahim-Bathis and Ahmed (2016)	Simulate rainfall-runoff	HEC-HMS	Arid	Ungauged	Doddahalla watershed, India
Ranjan and Singh (2022)	Simulate rainfall-runoff	HEC-HMS	Arid	Ungauged	Punpun river basin, India

4. Conclusion

This study examined the utilization of hydrological modelling in the framework of runoff as well as flooding. Water Balance Models have emerged as crucial tools for analyzing these events. They are extensively employed in the water resource management, and their associated risks were assessed. Hydrological models are used in water resource management, including urban hydrology and human activities. Combining Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with hydrological models provides considerable benefits, especially in simulating and forecasting runoff and flooding.

This review examines several crucial elements of hydrological modeling, including hydrology and watershed models, precipitation data, soil data, digital elevation model data, land cover data and land use, and the models HEC-RAS, SWAT, and HEC-HMS.

Hydrological models are instrumental in analyzing various hydrological phenomena, including direct runoff, runoff volume, and channel and base flow, and are applicable to both

gauged and ungauged catchments across diverse climatic conditions. In dry areas, there is an increased demand for experts to tackle the issues associated with hydrological modeling. For instance, specialists should investigate new approaches to assess the spatial distribution of infiltration and precipitation from temporary streams that lead to flash floods. Remote sensing (RS) data is usable to simulate events in arid regions, thereby reducing the need for detailed field monitoring. Consequently, observational data accumulated from the field and contrast with the results of the hydrological models. This review demonstrated that the extensive application of hydrological models in humid, semi-arid, and arid zones carry the effectively predict inundation areas, flood peaks, and runoff using distributed, semi-distributed, and lumped models, where all data entry for a basin is considered as a sole factor. This approach enhances the accuracy and reliability of runoff predictions. Recommendation: This review concludes that the application of hydrological models significantly benefits the water resource community, urban planners, and civil engineers in terms of understanding and managing surface and subsurface water resources for sustainable development. These models essential in evaluating and reducing flood risks. It is recommended that, given the increasing urbanization in various environments, the responsiveness of hydrological models to flood management should be analyzed further. This method must be conducted by analyzing a hydrological model. Hydrological modeling methods are essential tools in favor of catchment prediction and water management. To obtain more accurate results, it is advisable to employ two hydrological models for ungauged catchments. Therefore, this review strongly advocates the utilization of Digital Elevation Models (DEM) with high-resolution RS to simulate runoff, particularly in flat terrain areas.

References

- L. Deng, J. Yin, K. Chen, Y. Zeng, and S. Guo, "Multi-objective optimization of water resources allocation in Han River basin (China) integrating efficiency, equity and sustainability," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 798, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-04734-2.
- Z. Liu, X. Yang, Y. Lv, Z. Zhao, and J. Zhou, "Research on Water Resource Modelling Based on Machine Learning Technologies," *Water*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 472, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.3390/w16030472.
- J. H. Abdulkareem, W. N. A. Sulaiman, B. Pradhan, and N. R. Jamil, "Quantification of Runoff as Influenced by Morphometric Characteristics in a Rural Complex Catchment," *Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 145–162, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s41748-018-0043-0.
- V. Kumar and S. M. Yadav, "A state-of-the-Art review of heuristic and metaheuristic optimization techniques for the management of water resources," *Water Supply*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 3702–3728, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.2166/ws.2022.010.
- H. Solanki, U. Vegad, V. Mishra, and A. Kushwaha, "Improving Streamflow Prediction Using Multiple Hydrological Models and Machine Learning Methods," *Water Resources Research*, vol. 61, no. 1, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.1029/2024wr038192.
- M. I. Malik, S. A. Najjar, and M. S. Bhat, "Remote Sensing and GIS Based Groundwater Potential Mapping for Sustainable Water Resource Management of Lidder Catchment in Kashmir Valley, India," *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, vol. 87, no. 6, pp. 716–726, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s12594-016-0444-3.
- S. Pathak, D. Jato-Espino, R. D. Garg, C. S. P. Ojha, M. Liu, and R. P. Singh, "Spatiotemporal Analysis of Water Resources in the Haridwar Region of Uttarakhand, India," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 20, p. 8449, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12208449.
- H. Han and R. R. Morrison, "Data-driven approaches for runoff prediction using distributed data," *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 2153–2171, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00477-021-01993-3.
- B. S. Abdullaeva, "Integrating advanced approaches for climate change impact assessment on water resources in arid regions," *Journal of Water and Land Development*, pp. 149–156, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.24425/jwld.2024.149116.
- Y. Cheng, W. He, N. Cheng, and H. He, "The Effects of Climate and Anthropogenic Activity on Hydrologic Features in Yanhe River," *Advances in Meteorology*, vol. 2016, pp. 1–11, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1155/2016/5297158.
- S. Sugianto, A. Deli, M. Rusdi, E. Miswar, and M. Irham, "The Effect of Land Use and Land Cover Changes on Flood Occurrence in Teunom Watershed, Aceh Jaya," *Land*, vol. 11, no. 8, p. 1271, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.3390/land11081271.

Y. Li, Y. Wang, A. Guo, J. Chang, and W. Jin, “Spatiotemporal Impacts of Climate, Land Cover Change and Direct Human Activities on Runoff Variations in the Wei River Basin, China,” *Water*, vol. 8, no. 6, p. 220, May 2016, doi: 10.3390/w8060220.

Q. Huang *et al.*, “Using Remote Sensing Data-Based Hydrological Model Calibrations for Predicting Runoff in Ungauged or Poorly Gauged Catchments,” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 56, no. 8, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1029/2020wr028205.

M. A. Cardoso, M. C. Almeida, J. L. Gomes, R. S. Brito, P. Beceiro, and A. Oliveira, “1D/2D stormwater modelling to support urban flood risk management in estuarine areas: Hazard assessment in the Dafundo case study,” *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, vol. 13, no. 4, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1111/jfr3.12663.

B. Bhattacharya, R. Ugay, and M. Mazzoleni, “Flood Inundation Mapping of the Sparsely Gauged Large-Scale Brahmaputra Basin Using Remote Sensing Products,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 501, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.3390/rs11050501.

F. Radwan, A. Mossad, and A. Alazba, “Watershed morphometric analysis of Wadi Baish Dam catchment area using integrated GIS-based approach,” *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, vol. 10, no. 12, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s12517-017-3046-5.

M. Kencanawati, D. Iranata, and M. A. Maulana, “Hydrologic Modelling System HEC-HMS Application for Direct Runoff Determination,” *Journal of Human, Earth, and Future*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 153–165, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.28991/hef-2023-04-02-02.

P. A. Herrera, T. Hofmann, and M. A. Marazuela, “Parameter estimation and uncertainty analysis in hydrological modelling,” *WIREs Water*, vol. 9, no. 1, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1002/wat2.1569.

Y. Hou, H. Guo, W. Liu, and Y. Yang, “Global Evaluation of Runoff Simulation From Climate, Hydrological and Land Surface Models,” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 59, no. 1, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1029/2021wr031817.

M. Banjara, A. Bhusal, A. Kalra, and A. B. Ghimire, “Impact of Land Use and Land Cover Change on Hydrological Processes in Urban Watersheds: Analysis and Forecasting for Flood Risk Management,” *Geosciences*, vol. 14, no. 2, p. 40, Feb. 2024, doi.org/10.3390/geosciences14020040.

P. Song, J. Tian, and Y. Zhang, “Improving Surface Soil Moisture Estimates in Humid Regions by an Enhanced Remote Sensing Technique,” *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 48, no. 5, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1029/2020gl091459.

R. S. Khwairakpam and S. Kundu, “Significance of different probability distributions in flood frequency analysis of Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin, India,” *Discover Geoscience*, vol. 2, no. 1, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s44288-024-00072-8.

P. Deb and A. S. Kiem, "Evaluation of rainfall–runoff model performance under non-stationary hydroclimatic conditions," *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 65, no. 10, pp. 1667–1684, May 2020, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2020.1754420.

V. Manikanta and N. V. Umamahesh, "Performance assessment of methods to estimate initial hydrologic conditions for event-based rainfall-runoff modelling," *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 2277–2293, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.2166/wcc.2023.043.

M. Jajarmizad, M. Salarpour, and S. Harun, "A Review on Theoretical Consideration and Types of Models in Hydrology," *Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 249–261, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.3923/jest.2012.249.261.

A. N. A. Hamdan, M. Scholz, and S. Almuktar, "Rainfall-Runoff Modelling Using the HEC-HMS Model for the Al-Adhaim River Catchment, Northern Iraq," *Hydrology*, vol. 8, no. 2, p. 58, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/hydrology8020058.

I. M. Chathuranika *et al.*, "Comparison of Two Hydrological Models, HEC-HMS and SWAT in Runoff Estimation: Application to Huai Bang Sai Tropical Watershed, Thailand," *Fluids*, vol. 7, no. 8, p. 267, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.3390/fluids7080267.

X. Cheng, Q. Wang, X. Ma, Y. Xiao, X. Liu, and W. Wang, "Application of HEC-HMS Parameter Regionalization in Small Watershed of Hilly Area," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1961–1976, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11269-021-02823-5.

A. Amini, A. A. Aziz, S. M. Akib, A. H. B. Ghazali, and T. M. Ali, "Impacts of Land-Use Change on Streamflows in the Damansara Watershed, Malaysia," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 713–720, Aug. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s13369-011-0075-3.

M. Szwagrzyk, J. Kozak, D. Kaim, B. Price, E. Grabska, and A. Wypych, "Impact of forecasted land use changes on flood risk in the Polish Carpathians," *Natural Hazards*, vol. 94, no. 1, pp. 227–240, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11069-018-3384-y.

R. Cheah, F. Y. Teo, A. M. Alamri, A. Chan, L. Billa, and B. Pradhan, "Geospatial Modelling of Watershed Peak Flood Discharge in Selangor, Malaysia," *Water*, vol. 11, no. 12, p. 2490, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.3390/w11122490.

I. D. Skhakhfa and L. Ouerdachi, "Hydrological modelling of wadi Ressoul watershed, Algeria, by HEC-HMS model," *Journal of Water and Land Development*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 139–147, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1515/jwld-2016-0045.

R. Z. Harifidy, R. Z. M. Harivelo, M. Jun, I. Hiroshi, S. Kazuyoshi, and C. A. Fernández-Palomino, "Multi-gauge calibration comparison for simulating streamflow across the Major River Basins in Madagascar: SWAT + Toolbox, R-SWAT, and SWAT + Editor Hard calibration," *Hydrology Research*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 412–430, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.2166/nh.2024.188.

P. P. Mariani, O. C. Pedrollo, V. Sari, T. C. Schmitt, and N. M. Dos Reis Castro, “Different Infiltration Methods for Swat Model Seasonal Calibration of Flow and Sediment Production,” *Water Resources Management*, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 303–322, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11269-023-03671-1.

K. Haleem *et al.*, “Hydrological impacts of climate and land-use change on flow regime variations in upper Indus basin,” *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 758–770, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.2166/wcc.2021.238.

M. E. Lucas-Borja, B. G. Carrà, J. P. Nunes, L. Bernard-Jannin, D. A. Zema, and S. M. Zimbone, “Impacts of land-use and climate changes on surface runoff in a tropical forest watershed (Brazil),” *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 65, no. 11, pp. 1956–1973, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2020.1787417.

K. Wang, D. Yue, and H. Zhang, “Runoff Simulation of the Upstream Watershed of the Feiling Hydrological Station in the Qinhe River Based on the SWAT Model,” *Water*, vol. 16, no. 7, p. 1044, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.3390/w16071044.

M. L. Tan, A. L. Ibrahim, Z. Yusop, Z. Duan, and L. Ling, “Impacts of land-use and climate variability on hydrological components in the Johor River basin, Malaysia,” *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 1–17, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2014.967246.

D. Bekele, A. Kebede, A. M. Melesse, G. Zeleke, and T. Alamirew, “Modelling the impacts of land use and land cover dynamics on hydrological processes of the Keleta watershed, Ethiopia,” *Sustainable Environment*, vol. 7, no. 1, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1080/27658511.2021.1947632.

M. Iqbal, M. U. Masood, J. Wen, M. Adnan, and M. Masood, “Impacts of Climate and Land-Use Changes on Hydrological Processes of the Source Region of Yellow River, China,” *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 22, p. 14908, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su142214908.

K. Paiva, W. Lavado-Casimiro, F. Frappart, P. Rau, C. Montesinos, and L. Bourrel, “Hydrological Response Assessment of Land Cover Change in a Peruvian Amazonian Basin Impacted by Deforestation Using the SWAT Model,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 15, no. 24, p. 5774, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.3390/rs15245774.

R. Briones, N. Bantayan, and V. Ella, “Hydrologic Impact Evaluation of Land Use and Land Cover Change in Palico Watershed, Batangas, Philippines Using the SWAT Model,” *Journal of Environmental Science and Management*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 96–107, Jun. 2016, doi: [10.47125/jesam/2016_1/10](https://doi.org/10.47125/jesam/2016_1/10).

R. Bakhtyar *et al.*, “A New 1D/2D Coupled Modelling Approach for a Riverine-Estuarine System Under Storm Events: Application to Delaware River Basin,” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, vol. 125, no. 9, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1029/2019jc015822.

P. V. Timbadiya, P. L. Patel, and P. D. Porey, “A 1D–2D Coupled Hydrodynamic Model for River Flood Prediction in a Coastal Urban Floodplain,” *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 2, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1061/(asce)he.1943-5584.0001029.

D. Dutta, J. Alam, M. Hayashi, S. Hironaka, and K. Umeda, “A two-dimensional hydrodynamic model for flood inundation simulation: a case study in the lower Mekong river basin,” *Hydrological Processes*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 1223–1237, Apr. 2007, doi: 10.1002/hyp.6682.

A.-E. K. Vozinaki, G. G. Morianou, D. D. Alexakis, and I. K. Tsanis, “Comparing 1D and combined 1D/2D hydraulic simulations using high-resolution topographic data: a case study of the Koiliaris basin, Greece,” *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 642–656, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2016.1255746.

M. Waseem, S. Ahmad, I. Ahmad, H. Wahab, and M. K. Leta, “Urban flood risk assessment using AHP and geospatial techniques in swat Pakistan,” *SN Applied Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 8, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s42452-023-05445-1.

E. Huțanu, A. Grozavu, A. Mișu-Pintilie, A. Urzica, L. E. Paveluc, and C. C. Stoleriu, “Using 1D HEC-RAS Modelling and LiDAR Data to Improve Flood Hazard Maps Accuracy: A Case Study from Jijia Floodplain (NE Romania),” *Water*, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 1624, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.3390/w12061624.

J. Y.-A. Iroume *et al.*, “The 21st August 2020 Flood in Douala (Cameroon): A Major Urban Flood Investigated with 2D HEC-RAS Modelling,” *Water*, vol. 14, no. 11, p. 1768, May 2022, doi: 10.3390/w14111768.

A. S. Chen, S. Djordjević, J. Leandro, and D. A. Savić, “An analysis of the combined consequences of pluvial and fluvial flooding,” *Water Science and Technology*, vol. 62, no. 7, pp. 1491–1498, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.2166/wst.2010.486.

I. Fathy, H. F. Abd-Elhamid, and A. Ahmed, “Integrated management of surface water and groundwater to mitigate flood risks and water scarcity in arid and semi-arid regions,” *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, vol. 14, no. 3, May 2021, doi: 10.1111/jfr3.12720.

B. A. Devantier and A. D. Feldman, “Review of GIS Applications in Hydrologic Modelling,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 119, no. 2, pp. 246–261, Mar. 1993, doi: 10.1061/(asce)0733-9496(1993)119:2(246).

A. Fadil, H. Rhinane, A. Kaoukaya, O. A. Bachir, and Y. Kharchaf, “Hydrologic Modelling of the Bouregreg Watershed (Morocco) Using GIS and SWAT Model,” *Journal of Geographic Information System*, vol. 03, no. 04, pp. 279–289, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.4236/jgis.2011.34024.

A. Banerjee, P. Singh, and K. Pratap, “Morphometric evaluation of Swarnrekha watershed, Madhya Pradesh, India: an integrated GIS-based approach,” *Applied Water Science*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1807–1815, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s13201-015-0354-3.

P. K. Rai, B. Sajan, A. Singh, V. N. Mishra, A. P. Shahi, and P. Singh, “Geospatial Approach for Quantitative Drainage Morphometric Analysis of Varuna River Basin, India,” *Journal of Landscape Ecology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 1–25, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.2478/jlecol-2019-0007.

H. Aksoy, V. S. O. Kirca, H. I. Burgan, and D. Kellecioglu, "Hydrological and hydraulic models for determination of flood-prone and flood inundation areas," *Proceedings of the International Association of Hydrological Sciences*, vol. 373, pp. 137–141, May 2016, doi: 10.5194/piahs-373-137-2016.

H. Elewa, A. Nosair, and M. Zelenakova, "Integration of the Analytical Hierarchy Process and GIS Spatial Distribution Model to Determine the Possibility of Runoff Water Harvesting in Dry Regions: Wadi Watir in Sinai as a Case Study," *Water*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 804, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/w13060804.

Y.-P. Lin, N.-M. Hong, P.-J. Wu, and C.-J. Lin, "Modelling and assessing land-use and hydrological processes to future land-use and climate change scenarios in watershed land-use planning," *Environmental Geology*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 623–634, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.1007/s00254-007-0677-y.

A. Bronstert, D. Niehoff, and G. Bürger, "Effects of climate and land-use change on storm runoff generation: present knowledge and modelling capabilities," *Hydrological Processes*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 509–529, Jan. 2002, doi: 10.1002/hyp.326.

T. H. Bennett and J. C. Peters, "Continuous Soil Moisture Accounting in the Hydrologic Engineering Center Hydrologic Modelling System (HEC-HMS)," Sep. 2000, vol. 1110, pp. 1–10. doi: 10.1061/40517(2000)149.

G. Kan *et al.*, "Study on Applicability of Conceptual Hydrological Models for Flood Forecasting in Humid, Semi-Humid Semi-Arid and Arid Basins in China," *Water*, vol. 9, no. 10, p. 719, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.3390/w9100719.

S. N. Anuthaman, S. Ramasamy, B. Lakshminarayanan, and B. Ramasubbu, "Modelling and forecasting of urban flood under changing climate and land use land cover," *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, vol. 14, no. 12, pp. 4314–4335, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.2166/wcc.2023.164.

G. S. Dwarakish and B. P. Ganasri, "Impact of land use change on hydrological systems: A review of current modelling approaches," *Cogent Geoscience*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 1115691, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1080/23312041.2015.1115691.

H. Li, X. Zhou, and Y. Zhang, "Predicting Surface Runoff from Catchment to Large Region," *Advances in Meteorology*, vol. 2015, pp. 1–13, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1155/2015/720967.

M. Bermúdez, J. Puertas, and L. Cea, "A rapid flood inundation model for hazard mapping based on least squares support vector machine regression," *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, vol. 12, no. S1, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1111/jfr3.12522.

M. Jehanzaib, M. Ajmal, T.-W. Kim, and M. Achite, "Comprehensive Review: Advancements in Rainfall-Runoff Modelling for Flood Mitigation," *Climate*, vol. 10, no. 10, p. 147, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/cli10100147.

- A. I. Pathan and P. G. Agnihotri, "Application of new HEC-RAS version 5 for 1D hydrodynamic flood modelling with special reference through geospatial techniques: a case of River Purna at Navsari, Gujarat, India," *Modelling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1133–1144, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40808-020-00961-0.
- N. Dhakal, W. H. Asquith, D. B. Thompson, T. G. Cleveland, X. Fang, and L. J. Marzen, "Estimation of Volumetric Runoff Coefficients for Texas Watersheds Using Land-Use and Rainfall-Runoff Data," *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering*, vol. 138, no. 1, pp. 43–54, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1061/(asce)ir.1943-4774.0000368.
- M. El Alfy, "Assessing the impact of arid area urbanization on flash floods using GIS, remote sensing, and HEC-HMS rainfall–runoff modelling," *Hydrology Research*, vol. 47, no. 6, pp. 1142–1160, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.2166/nh.2016.133.
- D. Singh, S. P. Mcdermid, M. J. Puma, M. Kelley, B. I. Cook, and L. Nazarenko, "Distinct Influences of Land Cover and Land Management on Seasonal Climate.," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 123, no. 21, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1029/2018jd028874.
- F. Unduche, H. Tolossa, D. Senbeta, and E. Zhu, "Evaluation of four hydrological models for operational flood forecasting in a Canadian Prairie watershed," *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 63, no. 8, pp. 1133–1149, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2018.1474219.
- S. Grimaldi, A. Petroselli, and F. Nardi, "A parsimonious geomorphological unit hydrograph for rainfall–runoff modelling in small ungauged basins," *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 73–83, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2011.636045.
- H. A. Loaiciga, "Watershed Hydrology, 2nd Edition," *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*, vol. 77, no. 35, p. 340, Aug. 1996, doi: 10.1029/eo077i035p00340.
- M. O. D. Paula Netto, A. A. Ferreira, V. S. Coimbra, M. L. Lagarez Junior, and C. H. B. Rocha, "Comparative Analysis of SWAT and HEC-HMS Models for Efficient Watershed Management," *Revista de Gestão Social e Ambiental*, vol. 18, no. 11, p. e09931, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.24857/rgsa.v18n11-185.
- M. A. Aliye, T. Tadesse, P. Yohannes, and A. O. Aga, "Evaluating the Performance of HEC-HMS and SWAT Hydrological Models in Simulating the Rainfall-Runoff Process for Data Scarce Region of Ethiopian Rift Valley Lake Basin," *Open Journal of Modern Hydrology*, vol. 10, no. 04, pp. 105–122, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.4236/ojmh.2020.104007.
- R. Sith and K. Nadaoka, "Comparison of SWAT and GSSHA for High Time Resolution Prediction of Stream Flow and Sediment Concentration in a Small Agricultural Watershed," *Hydrology*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 27, May 2017, doi: 10.3390/hydrology4020027.
- C. Wilson and Q. Weng, "Assessing Surface Water Quality and Its Relation with Urban Land Cover Changes in the Lake Calumet Area, Greater Chicago," *Environmental Management*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1096–1111, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1007/s00267-010-9482-6.

M. R. Knebl, Z.-L. Yang, K. Hutchison, and D. R. Maidment, “Regional scale flood modelling using NEXRAD rainfall, GIS, and HEC-HMS/RAS: a case study for the San Antonio River Basin Summer 2002 storm event,” *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 75, no. 4, pp. 325–336, Mar. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2004.11.024.

A. Loukas and L. Vasiliades, “Streamflow simulation methods for ungauged and poorly gauged watersheds,” *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 1641–1661, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.5194/nhess-14-1641-2014.

K. G. Jencso and B. L. McGlynn, “Hierarchical controls on runoff generation: Topographically driven hydrologic connectivity, geology, and vegetation,” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 47, no. 11, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1029/2011wr010666.

X. Yang, J. Magnusson, J. Rizzi, and C.-Y. Xu, “Runoff prediction in ungauged catchments in Norway: comparison of regionalization approaches,” *Hydrology Research*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 487–505, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.2166/nh.2017.071.

Q. Li, G. Wang, B. Xue, H. Wang, Y. Peng, and X. Hu, “A Combined Method for Estimating Continuous Runoff by Parameter Transfer and Drainage Area Ratio Method in Ungauged Catchments,” *Water*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 1104, May 2019, doi: 10.3390/w11051104.

Y. Zhang *et al.*, “Can Remotely Sensed Actual Evapotranspiration Facilitate Hydrological Prediction in Ungauged Regions Without Runoff Calibration?, ” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 56, no. 1, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1029/2019wr026236.

A. Halefom, E. Sisay, L. Singh, T. Worku, and D. Khare, “Hydrological modelling of urban catchment using semi-distributed model,” *Modelling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 683–692, May 2017, doi: 10.1007/s40808-017-0327-7.

M. Saber and E. Habib, “Flash Floods Modelling for Wadi System: Challenges and Trends,” *Springer*, 2015, pp. 317–339. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-18787-7_16.

M. Hrachowitz *et al.*, “A decade of Predictions in Ungauged Basins (PUB)—a review,” *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1198–1255, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2013.803183.

R. Arsenault, M. Breton-Dufour, A. Poulin, G. Dallaire, and R. Romero-Lopez, “Streamflow prediction in ungauged basins: analysis of regionalization methods in a hydrologically heterogeneous region of Mexico,” *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 1297–1311, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1080/02626667.2019.1639716.

A. Msilini, C. Charron, T. B. M. J. Ouarda, and P. Masselot, “Flood frequency analysis at ungauged catchments with the GAM and MARS approaches in the Montreal region, Canada,” *Canadian Water Resources Journal / Revue canadienne des ressources hydriques*, vol. 47, no. 2–3, pp. 111–121, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1080/07011784.2022.2044385.

I. Pivovarova *et al.*, “Use of MLCM3 Software for Flash Flood Modelling and Forecasting,” *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 177–185, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.12911/22998993/79419.

H. Meresa, “Modelling of river flow in ungauged catchment using remote sensing data: application of the empirical (SCS-CN), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Hydrological Model (HEC-HMS),” *Modelling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 257–273, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s40808-018-0532-z.

N. Bulygina, N. McIntyre, and H. Wheeler, “Bayesian conditioning of a rainfall-runoff model for predicting flows in ungauged catchments and under land use changes,” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 47, no. 2, Feb. 2011, doi: 10.1029/2010wr009240.

K. Ibrahim-Bathis and S. A. Ahmed, “Rainfall-runoff modelling of Doddahalla watershed—an application of HEC-HMS and SCN-CN in ungauged agricultural watershed,” *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, vol. 9, no. 3, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s12517-015-2228-2.

S. Ranjan and V. Singh, “HEC-HMS based rainfall-runoff model for Punpun river basin,” *Water Practice and Technology*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 986–1001, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.2166/wpt.2022.033.

J. G. Arnold, R. Srinivasan, R. S. Muttiah, and J. R. Williams, “LARGE AREA HYDROLOGIC MODELLING AND ASSESSMENT PART I: MODEL DEVELOPMENT,” *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 73–89, Feb. 1998, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.1998.tb05961.x>.

X. Li *et al.*, “Watershed System Model: The Essentials to Model Complex Human-Nature System at the River Basin Scale,” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 123, no. 6, pp. 3019–3034, Mar. 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017jd028154>.

G. W. Brunner, “HEC-RAS River Analysis System: User's Manual,” *US Army Corps of Engineers, Institute for Water Resources*, 2001, Available: <https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/confluence/rasdocs/rasum/latest>.

H. Tamiru and M. Wagari, “Machine-learning and HEC-RAS integrated models for flood inundation mapping in Baro River Basin, Ethiopia,” *Modelling Earth Systems and Environment*, Jul. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-021-01175-8>.

H. M. Raghunath, *Hydrology*. New Age International (P) Ltd., 2006. Available: https://mlsu.ac.in/econtents/4167_Hydrology_Principles-H%20M%20RAGHUNATH%20.pdf

I. Fathy, A. M. Negm, Magid El-Fiky, M. Nassar, and Eman Al-Sayed, “RUNOFF HYDROGRAPH MODELLING FOR ARID REGIONS (CASE STUDY: WADI SUDR–SINAI),” vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 58–68, Jan. 2015, Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309494447_RUNOFF_HYDROGRAPH_MODELLIN_G_FOR_ARID_REGIONS_CASE_STUDY_WADI_SUDR-SINAI.